

Spectral and Magnetic Studies on Oxovanadium(IV) and Copper(II) Complexes with Tridentate Ligands

S. N. SHETTI**^a, A. S. R. MURTY^a and G. L. TEMBE*^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Karnatak University, Dharward-580 003

^bResearch Centre, Indian Petrochemicals Corporation Limited, Baroda-391 346

Manuscript received 13 September 1993, revised 23 June 1994, accepted 22 July 1994

Isonitrosoacetophenone thiosemicarbazone (INAPT) and 4-chloroisonitrosoacetophenone thiosemicarbazone (Cl.INAPT) react with oxovanadium(IV) chloride and copper(II) chloride forming complexes of the type VO(L-H)Cl and Cu(L-H)Cl. The thiocarbonyl hydrazone ligands coordinate to the central metal through S (thiocarbonyl), N (oximino) and N (azomethine) atoms.

Thiosemicarbazides and thiosemicarbazones find several applications as sensitive and selective reagents in the detection and determination of various metal ions¹. In these complexes the coordination of the ligand takes place through sulphur, nitrogen or both. In addition, many of these compounds possess a wide spectrum of medicinal properties². The transition metal complexes of these polydentate ligands present interesting spectral and stereochemical features³.

The present communication reports the complexes of oxovanadium(IV) and copper(II) with some thiosemicarbazones.

Results and Discussion

The physical and analytical data of all the complexes (Table 1) corresponds to 1 : 1 [M(L).X] metal : ligand (M = VO^{IV}, Cu^{II}; X = Cl, NO₃ and CH₃COO) stoichiometry. They are sparingly soluble in common organic solvents. The observed conductance values of 10.4–29.1 in methanol and 5.3–38.1 Ω⁻¹ cm⁻² mol⁻¹ in DMF characterise the complexes as non-electrolytes⁴. Owing to the limited solubility of the complexes the molecular weights could not be determined.

The ir spectra of INAPT and Cl.INAPT exhibit medium sharp band around 3 420 cm⁻¹(OH) similar to many isonitrosoketones⁵. The disappearance of this ligand band and appearance of a very broad band in this region in the complexes indicate the deprotonation

of =NOH group⁶. The δ_{NH} band due to terminal amino groups (3 200 cm⁻¹) remains almost unaltered on complexation indicating non-involvement of the NH group in coordination. A positive shift of 2–78 cm⁻¹ in $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ vibrations (~1 620 cm⁻¹) in case of the complexes implies the participation of N of C=N group coordination⁷. The slight positive or no shift of the band at 1 580 cm⁻¹(δ_{NH}) substantiates non-involvement of N bonding of NH group. Further evidence for the N bonding of the C=N group to the central metal ions stems from the shift to higher frequency (5–45 cm⁻¹) of $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ band (900 cm⁻¹) in all the complexes. Similarly, the coordination of N of oximino group is indicated by the shift of $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ (1 010 cm⁻¹) band to higher frequency⁸. The S of thioketo group coordinates to the central metal ion as the two characteristic bands of the composite $\nu_{\text{CS}} + \nu_{\text{CN}}$ (790–760 cm⁻¹) and ν_{CS} (692–670 cm⁻¹) undergo negative shift by 2–50 and 5–30 cm⁻¹ respectively, with reduction in intensity in a few cases on complexation⁹. Thus the ligands behave as tridentate monobasic with bonding occurring through N (imino), N (oximino) and S (thioketo) atoms. Further, the presence of $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ (~300), $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (450) and $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$ (240 cm⁻¹) bands in the far-infrared spectra supports the above conclusions.

Two strong bands due to acetate ion ν_{asy} OCO and ν_{sym} OCO appear at 1 578 and 1 414 cm⁻¹ in sodium acetate. The difference in the above two frequencies has been proposed for identifying the nature of ace-

**Present address : Department of Chemistry, ICL College, Vashi, New Bombay.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE VO^{IV} AND Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)						M.p °C	λ_M^* $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
	M	C	H	N	S	Cl		
[VO(INAPT-H)Cl] (Green)	15.55 (15.64)	33.22 33.40	2.68 2.80	17.22 17.31	9.83 9.91	10.79 10.95)	115	20.01 (29.25)
[VO(Cl.INAPT-H)Cl] (Green)	14.14 (14.23)	30.05 30.19	2.12 2.25	15.59 15.65	8.86 8.95	19.72 19.80)	125d	15.43 (21.12)
[Cu(INAPT-H)Cl] (Brown)	19.74 (19.84)	32.88 33.75	2.82 2.83	16.85 17.50	9.01 10.02	10.91 11.07)	179d	15.60 (5.35)
[Cu(INAPT-H)NO ₃] (Green)	18.21 (18.32)	31.12 31.17	2.34 2.62	19.99 20.19	9.01 9.24)	—	169	12.70 (7.49)
[Cu(INAPT-H)OAc] (Green)	18.41 (18.48)	38.29 38.42	3.30 3.52	16.22 16.29	9.21 9.32	—	198	29.14 (30.45)
[Cu(Cl.INAPT-H)Cl] (Brown)	17.84 (17.92)	30.25 30.48	2.15 2.27	15.72 15.80	8.98 9.04	19.84 19.99)	148	10.39 (20.43)
[Cu(Cl.INAPT-H)NO ₃] (Green)	16.59 (16.67)	28.08 28.35	2.03 2.12	18.31 18.37	8.34 8.41	9.19 9.30)	164d	15.32 (25.51)
[Cu(Cl.INAPT-H)OAc] (Green)	16.74 (16.80)	34.59 34.93	2.78 2.93	14.71 14.81	8.39 8.48	9.22 9.37)	159d	19.92 (21.39)

*In MeOH; values in parenthesis in DMF.

tate ion. For unidentate behaviour of acetate ion the separation is around 178 cm⁻¹. For the bidentate behaviour this separation is comparatively much lower as seen for example¹⁰ in [Ni (tet)OAc]ClO₄. The separation between the two observed bands in Cu(INAPT-H)OAc $\nu_{asy} \text{ OCO}$ (1 569), $\nu_{sym} \text{ OCO}$ (1 390 cm⁻¹) amounts to 186 and 140 cm⁻¹ respectively, suggesting unidentate coordination. For a bridging acetate $\nu_{asy} \text{ OCO}$ appears at 1 600 cm⁻¹, the latter possibility being overruled. The bands due to the nitrate group, namely, ν_1 (symmetric stretching) and ν_4 (doubly degenerate in-plane bending) appear at 1 384 (ν_1) and 1 494 cm⁻¹ (ν_4) in [Cu(INAPT-H)NO₃] and at 1 375 (ν_1) and 1 485 cm⁻¹ (ν_4) in [Cu(Cl.INAPT-H)NO₃]. The difference between ν_1 and ν_4 (110 cm⁻¹) corresponds with those associated with terminally bonded monodentate nitrate groups¹¹.

The corrected values of magnetic moments of [VO(INAPT-H)Cl] and [VO(Cl.INAPT-H)Cl] are 1.66 and 1.68 B.M. which are close to the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) for one unpaired electron, suggesting monomeric nature of these complexes and the absence of metal-metal interaction. The μ_{eff} values for the Cu^{II} complexes are in the range 1.24–1.71 B.M. which is

less than the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.). Since the planar copper(II) complexes are more prone to metal-metal interaction along the axial positions, the lowering in magnetic moments could possibly be due to these interactions. In view of the tridentate nature of the ligands and chemical composition, planar stereochemistry is proposed for these complexes¹².

The assignment of *d-d* transitions occurring in oxovanadium(IV) complexes are especially controversial. Though many models have been proposed to interpret the spectra of VO^{IV} complexes, the molecular model by Ballhausen and Gray¹⁴ is widely accepted. The BG scheme followed in the assignment of the observed bands in the electronic spectra of our complexes can be applied for ligands which lie above H₂O in the spectrochemical series¹⁴. This holds good for the thiosemicarbazones as they lie above the ligand H₂O¹⁵. The crystal field transitions in VO^{IV} (3d¹ ion) involve moving the electron in the lowest state ²B₂ to ²E, ²B₁ and ²A₁ excited states in the order of increasing energy¹⁶. For the present complexes the energy associated with the various transitions is shown below considering C_{4v} tetragonal symmetry :

$${}^2E \leftarrow {}^2B_2 \quad -3D_s + 5Dt \quad (12\ 900-13\ 100 \text{ cm}^{-1})$$

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL PARAMETERS OF VO^{IV} COMPLEX OF ISONITROSOKETONETHIOSEMICARBAZONE (IN DMF)*

Compd.	ν_1 cm ⁻¹	ν_2 cm ⁻¹	ν_3 cm ⁻¹	Dq cm ⁻¹	Ds	Dt	DQ	DS	DT	DT/DQ	ν_2/ν_1	μ_{eff} B.M.
[VO(INAPT-H)Cl]	12 900 (11 900)	16 500 (15 300)	26 800 (22 800)	1 650.0 (1 530.0)	-3 314.3 (-2 771.4)	591.4 (717.1)	35 880 (30 565)	23 200 (19 399)	8 017.1 (9 720.8)	0.22 (0.31)	1.28 (1.29)	1.66
[VO(Cl.INAPT-H)Cl]	13 100 (11 900)	16 600 (14 500)	28 500 (23 800)	1 660.0 (1 450.0)	-3 571.1 (-3 028.5)	477.1 (562.8)	37 988 (30 840)	24 999 (21 199)	6 467.6 (7 629.5)	0.17 (0.24)	1.27 (1.22)	1.68

*Values in paranthesis were obtained in nujol.

$${}^2B_1 \leftarrow {}^2B_2 \quad 10Dq \quad (16\,500\text{--}16\,600\text{ cm}^{-1})$$

$${}^2A_1 \leftarrow {}^2B_2 \quad 10Dq - 4Ds - 5Dt \quad (26\,800\text{--}28\,500\text{ cm}^{-1})$$

The ν_3 and ν_2 bands are relatively well defined in DMF than in the solid. On the other hand, ν_1 band is strong in the solid state as well as in solution. Since the electronic dipole vectors transform as A_1 and E in C_{4v} symmetry, only transitions to B_1 and E excited states are orbitally allowed. This ${}^2E \leftarrow {}^2B_2$ transition is expected to have somewhat greater intensity than the other crystal field transitions. This is observed in case of the present complexes. The position of the bands located by various authors for the support of expected C_{4v} symmetry, based on the BG scheme, are in the same region as found in the present case. The values for various crystal field parameters (Table 2) are in close agreement with those reported¹⁷ for tetragonally distorted octahedral VO^{IV} complexes.

The Cu^{II} complexes are subjected to considerable

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COPPER(II) ISONITROSOKETONETHIOSEMICARBAZONE (IN DMF)*

Compd.	${}^2B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ cm ⁻¹	${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ cm ⁻¹	C.T cm ⁻¹	Dq cm ⁻¹	μ_{eff} B.M.
[Cu(INAPT-H)Cl]	13 500 (13 800)	23 800 (23 800)	27 700 (29 500)	1 350 (1 380)	1.71
[Cu(INAPT-II)NO ₃]	13 800 (13 800)	23 400 (20 800)	28 900 (28 400)	1 380 (1 380)	1.49
[Cu(INAPT-H)OAc]	15 100 (14 500)	22 900 (22 700)	27 700 (27 700)	1 510 (1 510)	1.24
[Cu(Cl.INAPT-H)Cl]	15 100 (14 200)	22 200 (23 300)	29 400 (30 300)	1 510 (1 420)	1.65
[Cu(Cl.INAPT-II)NO ₃]	13 200 (14 200)	23 200 (22 700)	27 900 (28 700)	1 320 (1 420)	1.65
[Cu(Cl.INPAT-H)OAc]	13 100 (14 400)	22 700 (24 500)	28 900 (30 300)	1 310 (1 440)	1.54

*Values in parenthesis obtained in nujol.

Jahn-Teller distortion (since the ground state is $2E_g$) rendering their absorption spectra quite complex and in practice the majority of Cu^{II} complexes which are usually green or blue are tetragonally distorted with four short metal-ligand bonds in one plane (xy) and two longer metal-ligand bonds lying along the z -axis above and below this plane. The structure of the complex probably being a distorted octahedral which in the limiting case goes to square-planar configuration. The green Cu^{II} complexes in the present study display three prominent bands at 13 500–15 100, 22 700–24 500 and 27 700–30 300 cm⁻¹ (in solution and in the solid) which are assigned to ${}^2B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$, ${}^2E \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ and intra-ligand transition (π - π transition of the azomethine group¹⁸) which are characteristic of square-planar geometry¹⁹. The band positions for the two reddish brown [Cu(INAPT-H)Cl] and Cu[Cl.INAPT-H)Cl] complexes are similar to those observed in the nitrate and acetate complexes indicating square-planar geometry around Cu^{II} in the chloro complexes also. Unfortunately, it is not possible to determine the values for the inter-electronic repulsion parameters since all d - d transitions take place within the components of the same free ion term 2D (Ref. 20). Only the $10Dq$ value has been evaluated from the ${}^2B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ transition (Table 3). The room temperature esr spectra of powdered VO^{IV} complexes derived from INAPT and Cl.INAPT were measured. The g values were obtained by comparison with the resonance positions of a 0.1% DPPH in solid KCl. The g_{\perp} and g_{\parallel} values computed from the spectra are recorded in Table 4.

The delocalisation of in-plane π -antibonding and out-of-plane antibonding increases in the order of the covalency of the metal-ligand bond which is shown by increase in spin-orbit coupling constant. The order

TABLE 4—ESR SPECTRAL PARAMETERS OF VO^{IV} COMPLEXES WITH ISONITROSOKETONETHIOSEMICARBAZONE

Compd.	g_{\perp}	g_{\parallel}	g_{av}	λ_{\perp} cm ⁻¹	λ_{\parallel} cm ⁻¹	$\frac{\Delta g_{\parallel}}{\Delta g_{\perp}}$	$A_{\parallel} \times 10^4$ cm ⁻¹	$A_{\perp} \times 10^4$ cm ⁻¹
[VO(INAPT-H)Cl]	1.956	2.101	2.004	369.78	248.42	2.13	137.76	52.27
[VO(Cl.INPAT-H)Cl]	1.973	2.066	2.004	237.70	166.18	1.97	141.79	51.23

of energy-level in the electronic spectra (Table 2) can be tentatively fixed by employing the simple relationships,

$$\Delta g_{\perp} = g_{\perp} - 2.0023 \text{ and } \Delta g_{\parallel} = g_{\parallel} - 2.0023$$

if the ratio $\Delta g_{\parallel} / \Delta g_{\perp} > 4$; $b_2 (^2B_2)$ is above $e_g (^2E)$ and normal order prevails. On the otherhand, if $\Delta g_{\parallel} / \Delta g_{\perp} < 4$, then $b_2 (^2B_2)$ is below $e_g (^2E)$. This value being less than 4 in our VO^{IV} complexes further substantiates the assignments made in the electronic spectrum. The esr spectra on powdered sample reveal features of a tetragonally distorted Cu^{II} complex having $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state. The spectrum has one characteristic band with two g values. The g values obtained are compiled in Table 5. The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e (2.0023)$ observed in the present Cu^{II} complexes shows that the unpaired electron is localised in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of the Cu^{II} ion which is characteristic of axial symmetry. Copper(II) complexes with S-bonded ligands generally have g close to 2.03 and g_{\parallel} in the range 2.08–2.15 (Ref. 21). The g values (Table 5) suggest S coordination in the complexes which is in agreement with the infrared assignments discussed earlier. The G values [$G = (g_{\parallel} - 2) / (g_{\perp} - 2)$] estimated for the present com-

plexes is found to be less than four, which suggests exchange interaction between copper centres in the solid state²². The α^2 values (0.43–0.52) indicate appreciable in-plane covalency.

On the basis of the above discussion the following structures for the complexes is proposed :

Experimental

Preparation of ligands : Isonitrosoacetophenone was prepared from n-butylnitrile²³. Isonitrosoacetophenone thiosemicarbazone (INAPT) was prepared by condensing the ketone with thiosemicarbazide in presence of glacial acetic acid²⁴ as yellow crystals (80%) m.p. 176–77°. Similarly, chloroisonitrosoacetophenone thiosemicarbazone (Cl.INAPT) was synthesised in an analogous manner using 4-chloroacetophenone as the precursor as yellow crystals (75%) m.p. 147°.

Chloroisonitrosoacetophenone thiosemicarbazonato oxovanadium(IV) : Green syrupy vanadyl chloride was prepared from vanadium pentoxide²⁵. An ethanolic solution of VOCl₂ (2 mmol) was treated with an ethanolic solution of INAPT (2 mmol) with constant stirring. The solution was refluxed for 2–3 h and then slowly concentrated to a small volume. The thick

TABLE 5—ESR SPECTRAL PARAMETERS OF Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd.	g_{\perp}	g_{\parallel}	$A_{\parallel} \times 10^4$ cm ⁻¹	α^2	G
[Cu(INAPT-H)Cl]	2.065	2.222	82.99	0.52	3.415
[Cu(INAPT-H)NO ₃]	2.058	2.134	69.74	0.40	2.310
[Cu(INAPT-H)OAc]	2.063	2.203	77.12	0.43	3.222
[Cu(Cl.INAPT-H)Cl]	2.061	2.210	67.04	0.48	3.443
[Cu(Cl.INAPT-H)NO ₃]	2.060	2.155	75.47	0.43	2.583
[Cu(Cl.INAPT-H)OAc]	2.070	2.248	68.20	0.52	3.543

$$A_{\parallel} \text{ cm}^{-1} = [g > 4.6688 \times A(G)] \times 10^5; g \text{ is } g_{\parallel} \text{ value.}$$

semi-solid mass was cooled to 0° and extracted with petroleum-ether (b.p. 60–80°), whereby a green precipitate of the complex was obtained. It was then washed with a mixture of ethanol and petroleum-ether (1 : 1, v/v) till free from the reactants. The complex was then dried over P₂O₅ under vacuum for a period of 2 days, 62%, m.p. 115° (d).

Chloroisnitrosoacetophenone thiosemicarbazonato copper(II) : A hot aqueous ethanolic solution (25 ml) of CuCl₂·2H₂O (1 mmol) was added to a hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (1 mmol) and the mixture refluxed for 30 min. The reddish brown complex that separated out was washed with water, alcohol and ether, and dried over CaCl₂ under vacuum (yield 85%). Similar procedures were adopted for synthesising complexes of CLINAPT.

The elemental analysis of the complexes was carried out by standard methods²⁶. The conductivity was measured on an Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge using 10⁻³ M solution of the complexes in dimethylformamide and in methanol. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin Elmer 983 spectrophotometer, far-ir spectra on a Fourier FIR-30 instrument for solid samples suspended on polyethene plates in nujol mull, electronic spectra (DMF) on a Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer and esr powder spectra on a Varian E-4 x-band spectrometer using cylindrical quartz sample tube operating at 9.32 GHz using diphenylpicrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical as g marker. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature (26°) by the Gouy method using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as the calibrant. Magnetic moment values were corrected for diamagnetism of the ligands using Pascal's constants.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.N.S.) is thankful to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Teacher Research Fellowship.

References

1. R. B. SINGH, B. S. GARG and R. P. SINGH, *Talanta*, 1978, **25**, 619.
2. G. DOMAGK, R. B. BEINISCH, F. MIETZSCH and H. SCHMIDT, *Naturwiss.*, 1964, **33**, 315; H. G. PETERING and G. J. VAN GIESSEN, "The Biochemistry of Copper", Academic, New York, 1966, p. 197; K. C. AGARWAL and A. C. SARTORELLE in "Antineoplastic and Immunosuppressive Agents II", eds. A. C. SARTORELLI and D. C. JOHNS, Springer, New York, 1975.
3. V. M. LEOVAC, N. V. GERBELEU and V. D. CANIC, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **27**, 514; R. K. Y. HO, S. E. LIVINGSTONE and T. N. LOCKYER, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1966, **19**, 1179; Y. K. BHOON, S. MITRA, J. P. SCOVILL and D. L. KLAYMAN, *Transit. Met. Chem.*, 1982, **7**, 264.
4. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 110.
5. K. BURGER, "Coordination Chemistry, Experimental Methods", Butterworths, London, 1973; R. G. DESHMUKH, M.Sc. Thesis, University of Bombay, 1983.
6. M. NONOYAMA, S. TONITA and K. YAMASAKI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **12**, 33.
7. D. M. WILES, B. A. GINGRAS and T. SUPRUNCHUK, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1967, **45**, 469.
8. A. PALM and H. WERBIN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1954, **1**, 1004.
9. G. R. BURNS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 277.
10. N. F. CURTIS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1579; 1964, 2644.
11. N. F. CURTIS and Y. M. CURTIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 804; B. ZARLI, L. VOLPANI, L. SINDELLARI and C. G. DEPAOLI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 231.
12. Y. K. BHOON, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **5**, 365.
13. J. R. WASSON and H. J. STOKLOSA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 227.
14. C. J. BALLHAUSEN and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 111.
15. C. K. JORGENSEN, "Modern Aspects of Ligand Field Theory", North Holland, London, 1972.
16. D. KIVELSON and J. S. LEE, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, **41**, 1896.
17. R. C. PAUL, N. C. SHARMA, R. D. VERMA and N. K. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14** 705.
18. D. L. ARORA, K. LAL, S. P. GUPTA and S. K. SAHNI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 980.
19. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", Wiley, New York, 1965; J. S. RAO, K. L. REDDY, S. J. SWAMY and P. LINGAIAH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 942.

20. B. BOSNISCH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 627.
21. D. Y. WEST, R. M. MAKEEER, J. P. SCOVILL and D. L. KLAYMAN, *Polyhedron*, 1984, **3**, 947.
22. A. JAGGI, S. CHANDRA and K. K. SHARMA, *Polyhedron*, 1985, **4**, 163; B. J. HATHWAY, *Struct. Bond.*, 1973, **14**, 60.
23. F. J. WELCHER, "Organic Analytical Regents", Van Nostrand, New York, 1955, Vol. 3, p. 279.
24. N. SALDABOS, A. CIMANIS, S. HILLERS, J. POPELIS, L. N. ALEKSEEVA, A. ZILE and A. K. VALYNSKAYA, *Khim. Pharm. Zh.*, 1974, **8**, 12.
25. B. J. MCCORMIK, J. L. FEATHERSTONE, H. L. STOKLOSA and J. R. WASSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 692.
26. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text book of Quantitative Inorganic Analyses", ELBS, London, 1969.